

STUDENTS THE PROBLEM OF PREPARING FOR TEXT CREATION ACTIVITIES BY COMPLETING GRAMMAR TASKS

Tursunoy Yusupova

Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi
Mother tongue education department pedagogy sciences candidate, associate professor.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11090296>

Abstract. This in the article mother language in education applicable text, text content, text of types mutually differences and them Create to the process in preparation useful of assignments types and content about information given. Mother tongue in education applied grammar of assignments role, importance and types about Methodist scientists by reported to feedback analytical relationship reported. Also present in the day at school mother language in education in use grammar of assignments in textbooks given attitude to situations stated. Grammatical assignments content, as well as from it text Create and text on work in the process applied of assignments types illuminated and preparation process about recommendations given.

Keywords: text, grammar assignments, text types, text Create process, approach.

СТУДЕНТОВ ПРОБЛЕМА ПОДГОТОВКИ К ТЕКСТОБРАЗИТЕЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПУТЕМ ВЫПОЛНЕНИЯ ГРАММАТИЧЕСКИХ ЗАДАНИЙ

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается родной язык в образовании, применимый текст, текстовое содержание, текст типов взаимоотношений и их создание в процессе подготовки полезных типов и содержания заданий по предоставленной информации.

Родной язык в образовании применял грамматику ролей, важности и типов заданий об ученых-методистах согласно сообщенным аналитическим отношениям с обратной связью. Также в школе присутствует родной язык в обучении, используется грамматика заданий учебников с учетом отношения к изложенным ситуациям. Содержание грамматического задания, а также текста на его основе и текста по работе в процессе выполнения, освещены типы заданий и процесс подготовки, даны рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: текст, грамматические задания, типы текста, процесс создания текста, подход.

This article provides information about the text used in mother tongue education, the content of the text, the differences between text types, and the types and content of tasks useful in preparing them for the creation process. The content of grammar tasks, as well as the types of tasks used in the process of creation. An analytical response was given to the opinions expressed by Methodist scientists about the role, importance and types of grammatical tasks used in mother tongue education. At the same time, there was also a reaction to the cases of grammar tasks that are currently used in mother tongue education in school. The content of grammar tasks, as well as the types of tasks used in the process of creating a text and working on the text, and recommendations on the preparation process are given.

Keywords: text, grammar tasks, text types, text creation process, approach.

DTS requirements based on mother language education content update in fundamental reforms in the field theoretical knowledge take over equal to speech of growing up the first in the direction of of students word wealth expansion , second in the direction spelling and pronunciation

standards, as well as words categories and syntactic of structures methodical opportunities understanding, third in the direction the idea oral and written connected statement to do qualification and skills formation mean caught ¹Each direction requirements step by step forming to go occupied knowledge, skill and qualifications written in speech free apply to get and to the student someone topic within independent text Create opportunity creates

in DTS mother language science from teaching the goal in students oral and written speech skills, creativity thinking skills , reading and speech culture development the fact that defined is, and within the scope of science given theoretical knowledge in practice apply to the goal to redirect service who does support competencies and to science about competencies to know to levels suitable respectively is formed. In this to science about linguistic Competencies (FK1) phonetics, graphics, orthography, orthography, vocabulary, grammar and to methodology about theoretical knowledge requirements, speech competence while (FK2) listening to understand, read, speak, write circle requirements cover take set placed²

DTS National based on the curriculum improvement students exactly in practice to apply directed knowledge with arming opportunity surface brought Read the students vital to skills who prepares practical topics weight expanded. Mother tongue in education speech skills formation to the main level rising and listening understand, speak, read and to write competencies serious attention focused started In particular, mother language in education listening of understanding to understand, to understand such as stages on work through speech skills cognitive knowledge with tie take to go according to research work too let's go started Of these all of them of students connected to the speech circle skills formation and to develop directed note reach can

1999 DTS requirements based on created in textbooks of the tongue theoretical knowledge (FK 1). take over, that's it based on qualification and skills formation the first level calculated. Each to the topic circle in exercises new knowledge strengthening for assignments given. For exampl , the 6th grade "O na language" in the textbook" Word maker In the subject of suffixes - zor, - istan, -li suffixes using cherry, Uzbek, will from the basics new words to make, from the base understood meaning with new made word the meaning the difference explain assignment given in exercises 65-68 tasks are also a word maker additions determination and to determine directed . Only in the 2nd condition of exercise 67 " In the text to the idea will you join ?" the question meeting can In the text main the idea is ambitious children are the future of the country determine about be in observation to conduct referrer assignments not given DTS requirements in 2021 and National in the content of the curriculum pure speech skills development mean caught Long years during mother language education content grammar concepts to study focus, then while this of stage speech skills to develop towards change students by mother language education in possession spaces surface brought This is Methodist scientist Agulomov by emphasizing passed was: " As you know , a lot." cases mother language in training students occupying skills , mainly language grammar construction to learn focused on their word wealth increase, from the word right and appropriate use , the idea statement of doing efficient ways determination such as useful

¹ Hamroyev G' . Mother tongue in education study assignments work exit linguodidactic the basics improvement: Ped. science. Dr. (DSc) ... dis-ya . - Tashkent , 2022. - p. 72. 14

²Mother science language National curriculum . Republican Education Center . 2022/2023 academic year .

practical skills somewhat out of consideration outside remains. That's why for mother language program students more of this useful practical skills with to arm orientation must" ³.

Students mother from the language skill with efficient use if, own thoughts impressive, understandable statement do it if possible, from the ancestors the rest is rich scientific and artistic inheritance deep understanding level own language if he knows, that's it mother language education own to the goal achieved will be for this mother language in their classes used study materials language skills complex way to form directed to be it is necessary Once upon a time pronunciation, spelling, and words wealth increase, moreover, independent to thinking to redirect conditions Create language skills strengthening speech skill increases. Mother tongue of classes main purpose calculated of students connected speech qualifications formation, to him the ground creator phonetics, orthography, orthography, punctuation from exercises regularly use, tasks and exercises purposeful orientation this in progress efficient the result will give. Mother tongue education of students speech skills in development independent thinking with depends creative activities to form separately attention requires focus. In this regard Methodist scientist Sh. Yusupova's take went research work and by him recommendation done exercise and of assignments importance extremely big

It seems that the students connected to the speech in preparation their creative independent thinking abilities Cultivation is also grammatical knowledge to strengthen directed exercise and and the importance of assignments big That's two direction in harmony take to go of students written connected speech qualifications to develop service does And this them text make up skills forms . 5th grade students phonetic events , pronunciation and spelling rules of the word meaning features will learn is constant respectively being used of the word content in understanding to dictionaries appeal they do Today's globalization conditions young generation intellectual to potential have, high spiritual, national and universal to values loyal person as in education study to dictionaries need it is felt. After all, "linguistics to the front important socio-political order - mom from the language practical use efficiency increase and foreign languages fast to teach service doer school dictionaries Create task placed". For 6th grade intended assignments samples of those studied in the 5th grade repeat, new knowledge speech in the situation to apply based on The word couples find, new the words supporting sentences to compose, from sentences connected text in making in students Diligence, curiosity, rationality of thinking efficient results observed. In the 7th grade, students go to the " Morphology " section about knowledge with complete getting to know they come out. This is the class for intended assignments at work agreement, possession, plural of categories, duty-mate helper of words in the text to be used circle assignments Create the goal done. For 8th grade intended assignments basically communicative-cognitive competencies to form based on Students connected to the text preparation this period own the result showed. Summary by doing so to speak, connected text to create referrer grammar assignments perform

³ General medium of education state education standard and curriculum . Oh no language A nature . (grades 5–9) // Uzbekistan Republic the law documents collection . - To shkent ; 2017, No. 14 (774). Hamroyev G' . Mother tongue in education study assignments work exit linguodidactic the basics improvement : Ped. science. Dr. (DSc) ... dis- ya . - Tashkent, 2022. - p. 72. Mahmudov N. and others General medium education for the 6th grade of their schools mother language textbook . - Tashkent: Tasvir , 2017. - P. 25. 15

through students independent thought walk get ability have will be And this the students text Create to the activity in preparation very important is considered

To all of us As you know, the text on to work directed grammar assignments, that is expanding, condensing, editing, comparing, summarizing issues text on of work the most considerate aspects is considered Young in generation creative thinking and independent thinking skills formation important The student 's study material mastery complicated process is a language events observe acquisition, research, comparison, generality and individuality to determine the differences find, classify judgment release, use with depend This connection, especially the students with ready texts on work in the process obvious to the eye thrown away and linguistic knowledge enrichment with together speech skills to develop service does Read the students text on to work in teaching, that is expanding, condensing, editing, comparing, summarizing such as practical things in execution creative explain place and importance to emphasize necessary Because explain this in type student to the text image methods adding or linguistically and spelling assignments entered or teacher starting from gave the story continue made without statement to write can Process read the student text on to work directs.

Mother tongue in their classes students story text, image text, discussion texts on work through the following knowledge, skill and to qualifications have to be in the eye held:

- text from the content come out to him title to put
- the text scientific in observation so, then reflection delivered idea again statement to do
- from the text intended the goal understanding
- certain subject or events describe and to describe possibility Create;
- text on the surface for consideration enter;
- from comments conclusion issue
- feedback and conclusions around argue

Text on work in the process certain one text on the surface around thought conduct, text content expand, from the text issued the conclusion to condense, to edit the text attention is directed. Mother tongue in textbooks given all texts ready text as acceptance without doing it, that's it the text more expand, edit, compare, conclude such as in directions activity conduct to the goal according to Text on to work organize reach the students independent creative to thinking , own connected speech to develop sends⁴

⁴ Nurmonov A., Abduraimova M., Yusupova Sh. Statements set (General education V-IX classes of schools for).-T: Teacher , 1997. – p. 4. G'ulomov A., Ne'matov H. Mother tongue education content . - Tashkent: Teacher , 1995. - p. 4. Yusupova Sh. Mother tongue education efficiency increase and progress pedagogical technologies current achieve : ped science. nom-di diss. TDPI. - T., 1998. - p. 137 Bahriddinova BM in Uzbekistan study vocabulary : linguistic basics , history and prospects . Phil. science doc . (DSc).... diss. abstract . - S., 2020. - p. 14. Yusupova T. A. THE FORMS OF INTERRELATION WITH TOPICS OF SYNTAX IN REVISING MORPHOLOGY // Journal of Critical Reviews ISSN- 2394-5125 Vol 7, Issue 7, 2020 (Skopus). Yusupova T. A. To develop students' knowledge, skills and competencies in the organizational and technical aspects of essay // ACADEMICIA A n I nternat i onal M ult i d i sc i pl i nary R esearch J ournal (Double Blind Refereed & Peer Reviewed Journal) ISSN : 2249-7137 Vol. 11, Issue 2, February 2021 Impact Factor: SJIF 2021 = 7.492

Mother tongue in the lessons, the text expand to the process about assignments of students text on performance, editing and analysis opportunities increases. The student 's text on work in the activity the idea in consistency statement reach, expand, text language and style coordination through done if increased , the student speech competence formation and his in his mind own apply skill, situation administration get, moral their views right to develop directed cognitive and psycholinguistic views to form service does T. Ziyadova the text to compact in particular stops as "text content did not change without in the text there is has been superlatives : person and of the item complete image, biography situation, portrait, landscape appearances expression maximum level reduce the text from repetition cleaning, spelling, logical, methodical error words , sentences, phrases find them eliminate it's simple the sentences joint to words convert, joint the sentences word and from sentence expanders empty so, united piecemeal to words turn, lyric withdrawal, artistic of images appropriate-inappropriate definition, text to the content suitable not coming information and from inputs give up passing away or them reduce , paragraphs combine etc.⁵ mean holds Text on work in the process the text to compact in the student correct, appropriate, fluent, creative thinking , writing speech competencies to strengthen take will come. Text to compact text content save it from repetition cleaning, spelling, logical, methodical errors eliminate joint the sentences simple to the point to convert take will come. Read the student consistent, logical to thinking , others his opinion listening and to understand, thought product certain style and literary norms based on, correctly, fluently to express in teaching, of the language speech from the opportunity use competence in formation of text editing importance big G. Blinov "Punctuation errors description "⁶ in the article student text edit on work in facilitation efficient use possible has been recommendations work developed In the article recommendation according to the student first the text complete by reading output and of the text content understand take it is necessary The first shot is from winter corrections to input rush text the author idea without realizing it done increase due to to mistakes take coming can Text type and content about to the imagination have from division then , text linguistically if edited in terms of to the goal according to will be This is the place of words spelling , punctuation signs, methodical ignore the shortcomings outside not to leave it is necessary Editorial corrections in the process main in the text some places expansion , take disposal , handling to be given , to be changed can Mother tongue in education main attention students created in the texts observable spelling, punctuation , style to edit errors is directed . Classic texts in learning student today's from the norm distinguishable word and also edits attachments. In particular, the text to conclude complex, many p network, possible until problematic in character the text to learn directed will be Text in conclusion topic within of students thoughts discussion will be done. For example, in the text reflection reached of the problem positive and negative aspects, virtue and disadvantages, benefits and damages according to is studied. This process critical, analytical, clear makes sense thinking successful to develop and of students independent ideas , thoughts written and oral in the form systematic statement protection to do chance creates Today's day mother language in education main attention in students text on work through speech skills to take over directed so , mother language in textbooks

⁵ Ziyadova T. Text Create technology . - Tashkent: Science, 2007. - p. 43.

⁶Blinov G. Classification punctuatsionnyx lover. - Moscow: Vysshaya shkola, 1970. - 116 p. 18

in the text information in its reflection reached idea test tasks in the form of perform text content fast and easy to master possibility creates Text on of work this new direction improving students PISA international evaluation to the system preparation in the 8th grade textbook given texts based on speech and grammar skills to form service also recommend test samples to do can

Text of creation study material independent mastery, complexity level differently has been assignments, practical tasks creative and independent perform based on connected to the text directed systematic activity statement done Texts purpose, task, complexity level, to whom (individual or the team for) that it is intended looking at each other difference does Text Create in the process selected of subjects scientific, systematic, educational of materials fun, practice with connection, interdisciplinary relevance is also given texts and of assignments creative to the character ownership important Independent being studied of the subject practice with integrity, scientificity and study of materials interesting topics systematicity, assignment and of duties a lot edge, mutual dependence important place holds But, the most the main thing is the students text Create activities organize reach being, in this their aspiration and interests separately attention focus necessary Humanity own historical development during collected social of experiences certain part independent study activity only on the basis of take over take can Good preparation have was talented students creative and research feature have has been texts without difficulty they create Preparation must level was not of students texts simpler content occupation is connected text Create on regularly work them text Create skills development enable will give.

Students text to create in teaching the following Methodical recommendations attention to take should:

- text in creating of students young psychology, speech ability and opportunities account get
- text Create in the process mother language another sciences with mutual in relation learning principle justification;
- language events comparison, differentiation, selection, grouping, analysis and synthesis to do - text in creating student sensitivity increasing questions with appeal reach
- oral and written speech science and comprehensibility, coherence and continuity principle based on development;
- to the textbook addition as speech to grow exercises, problematic study assignments, psycholinguistics tests, topic based on control questions make up exercises input and them continuously by improving to go

5th grade "Mother tongue" textbook new in the publication "Nature and we", "Uzbek famous made "Allapinin", "Huge explosion", "Polar star", "On the phone talk cultur", "Alp Er Ton", "Bridges", "Constitution what?", "In fish mind is there?", "Algorithm founder", "Ancient such as " cities". history, mathematics, medicine, geography such as to the sciences about texts included. This is mother language education speech activity types (listening, reading, speaking, writing) of communication all in the fields right to use orientation if we say, we are not wrong. for the 6th and 7th grades in the 2022-2023 academic year National based on the curriculum new textbooks based on mother language teaching to the road was put General medium of education national study in the program language in education integrative approach main to the plan issued This is National study in the program: "Sciences mutually tie study, it or in this subject being

studied incident about in the pupil live in observation to do qualification grows. With this student incident about sure to the imagination have it will be," he said is emphasized. In the program "I, you, he and they", "Nature blessings" , "Healthy - healthy mind", "My profession is my pride", "Yosh Economist", "Science and technologies", "Language and language", "History treasures", "Art and culture", "Our right is our right" in chapters given texts learning efficiency increase for text based on structured test questions , discussion topics, project works given . From this intended the goal speech competence to develop directed become a process students like PISA, PIRLS international evaluation to systems prepares Such an approach in students text Create and him methodical editing skills harvest does and strengthens

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